

BLENDS OF POLY(ETHYLENE TEREPHTHALATE) AND EPOXY RESIN AS A MATRIX MATERIAL FOR CONTINUOUS FIBRE - REINFORCED COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Epoxy resin is applied as a reactive solvent for poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) to obtain solutions with a low melt-viscosity. These solutions are cured according to two different cure schedules, the first schedule curing in the melt and the second allowing for crystallization of the PET prior to curing. Blends cured in the melt show a phase-separated morphology with a decreased epoxy particle size. The flexural strength and strain to failure show an increase with increasing epoxy content, whereas blends cured in the melt show overall lower flexural properties, indicating degradation of PET. The flexural performance of glass fabric laminates with a PET / epoxy matrix confirm that the reactive processing route yields good quality composites. The laminate in-plane shear strength is increased with increasing epoxy content, which is in agreement with the increase in the matrix flexural properties and the increase in fibre-matrix adhesion due to the presence of epoxy resin.

KEYWORDS: reactive solvent, epoxy-modified thermoplast, phase separation, in-plane shear strength, fibre-matrix adhesion, polymer blends.

INTRODUCTION

New developments in fibre-reinforced thermoplastic composites are aiming at cost-effective composites which may attract large-volume markets such as the automotive industry. Since the cost-effectiveness of a product is strongly dependent on raw material costs, these developments are mainly focusing on low-cost materials like glass fibres as a reinforcement and commodity thermoplastics such as polypropylene (PP), polyamide (PA), poly(buthylene terephthalate) (PBT) and poly(ethylene terephthalate) (PET) as a matrix.

Glass fibre-reinforced composites based on thermoplastics are often produced by way of melt- or solution impregnation routes. Because of the relatively high melt viscosities of thermoplastic polymer melts, melt impregnation is often only achieved in the case of low molecular weight polymers, resulting in poor mechanical properties in terms of stiffness, strength and impact-resistance.

In the case of solution impregnation techniques, the solution provides a low viscosity medium that can easily impregnate the fibres. After impregnation the solvent has to be removed by conventional drying operations. However, the presence of residual solvent can result in a reduction in T_g and poor interface conditions, which is widely recognized as a major problem.

In order to overcome these drawbacks in conventional solution impregnation, a new processing route based on the use of epoxy resins as reactive solvents is currently under

development in our laboratory [1-5]. An interesting aspect of this reactive processing route is that in the case of fibre-reinforced composites the epoxy resin is not only an effective solvent, lowering the viscosity (for tractable polymers) and (or) the processing temperature (for intractable polymers) of the polymer matrix and thus acting as a processing aid during impregnation. After impregnation and shaping, the reactive solvent is polymerized and converted into a non-solvent. This initiates phase separation and, depending on the composition of the blend, phase inversion. As a consequence, a dispersed epoxy phase results, which is locked up inside the continuous thermoplastic phase. In this way the cured reactive solvent provides an essential structural part of the final material and contributes to interfacial adhesion between the fibre and the thermoplastic matrix [2, 4, 5].

In this paper we describe the use of epoxy resin as a reactive solvent for PET, a semi-crystalline engineering thermoplast. Next to this, we report on the application of these PET / epoxy blends as a matrix material for continuous glass fibre-reinforced composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

PET / epoxy blends

Materials and blend preparation

The PET used in this study (BX5662, $M_n = 25 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$, $M_w = 60 \text{ kg}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$) was kindly supplied by ICI. Prior to blending the PET granules were powdered and dried overnight at $150 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. As the reactive solvent a standard 2-functional epoxy resin, diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A (DGEBA, Araldite LY556, Ciba Geigy), with a molecular weight of $380 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ was used. The resin was cured with a stoichiometric amount of 4-functional amine curing agent, 4,4'-methylene bis(3-chloro-2,6-diethyl aniline) (M-CDEA), supplied by Lonza.

To study the viscosity of PET / DGEBA solutions, mixtures of PET and epoxy resin (in absence of curing agent) with a PET content of 40-100 wt.% were prepared in a miniature co-rotating twin screw extruder (6 cm^3 volume) at $260 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 40 rpm.

PET / epoxy blends (epoxy resin and curing agent) with a PET content of 50-100 wt.% were prepared by premixing the constituents and feeding this mixture into a Haake Rheomex type TW-100 twin-screw compounding extruder at $270 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 50 rpm screw-speed. After compounding the blends were compression moulded and cured to obtain 1.8 mm thick plates. Two different cure schedules were applied. In the first cure schedule (A) the epoxy was cured in the melt at $260 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, after which the PET was allowed to crystallize. The second cure schedule (B) allowed for crystallization of the PET at $180 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ prior to complete curing of the epoxy. A crystallization temperature of $180 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was selected because of the maximum in crystallization rate at this temperature for unmodified PET [6]. The different cure schedules applied are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Cure schedules for curing of the PET / DGEBA / M-CDEA blends

Cure schedule	Step 1	Step 2	Step 3
A	3 min at $260 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	40 min at $260 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	20 min at $180 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$
B	3 min at $260 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	180 min at $180 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$	

Rheology

The zero-shear viscosity of PET / DGEBA solutions at 260 °C was determined in the linear visco-elastic region using a Rheometrics type RDS-II Spectrometer. An oscillating parallel-plate test setup with 25 mm plates and a 0.8 mm gap distance was used.

Morphology

The morphology of the cured PET / epoxy blends was studied using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM, Cambridge Stereoscan 200). The samples for SEM observations were prepared by cryogenic fracture, etched by oxygen plasma for 10 minutes and finally coated with a thin gold/palladium layer.

Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of the cured blends were determined by three-point bending tests on a Zwick type 1445 testing machine. The three-point bending tests were performed according to the ASTM D790-86 standard (dimensions 50 x 25 x 1.9 mm) at a strain rate of 10^{-3} s^{-1} and at span-to-depth ratios of 16.

Composites based on PET / epoxy blends

Materials and composite manufacture

Six-ply laminates were manufactured from woven E-glass fibre 8H satin-weave fabric (SS0303-8203, $300 \text{ g}\cdot\text{m}^{-2}$, Ten Cate Advanced Composites). The matrix consisted of PET / epoxy blends with a PET content of 50-100 wt.%, which were prepared as described in the previous section. The composites were manufactured by stacking six layers of fabric alternately with layers of uncured and powdered PET / epoxy blend in a mould and subsequently moulding and curing them in a hot press at a pressure of 25 bar to obtain 1.9 mm thick plates. The different cure schedules applied are shown in Table 1. The total volume fraction of fibre in all laminates was approximately 40 %.

Mechanical properties

The mechanical properties of the six-ply laminates were determined by three-point bending and in-plane shear tests on a Zwick type 1445 testing machine. The three-point bending tests were performed on 0/90° coupons (dimensions 40 x 25 x 1.9 mm) according to the ASTM D790-86 standard at a strain-rate of 10^{-3} s^{-1} . Span-to-depth ratios of 16 were used. The in-plane shear tests were performed by uniaxial tensile tests on $\pm 45^\circ$ coupons (dimensions 160 x 20 x 1.9 mm) according to the ASTM D3518-91 and D3039-93 standards at a cross head speed of $2 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$. The shear modulus (G_{12}) was measured using both a longitudinal and a transverse extensometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Rheology of PET / epoxy resin solutions

In Figure 1 the zero-shear viscosities of homogeneous PET / DGEBA solutions at a temperature of 260 °C are presented. The viscosity of the PET used in this study (300 Pa·s at 260 °C) is low in comparison with melt-viscosities of other standard polymers commonly used ($10^3 - 10^5$ Pa·s). However, even lower viscosities are obtained for solutions of PET with epoxy resin. Upon increasing the epoxy resin content a dramatic decrease in viscosity is observed from 300 Pa·s for pure PET to a value of approximately 0.1 Pa·s at 60 wt.% epoxy resin. This low melt-viscosity is in the same range as for resins used in structural reaction injection moulding (SRIM) and in resin transfer moulding (RTM). In this way, our objective to lower the viscosity of the thermoplast in order to increase the impregnation rate and level of continuous-fibre reinforcements could certainly be achieved by using epoxy resin as a reactive solven

Figure 1: Zero-shear viscosities of PET / DGEBA solutions at 260 °C versus the epoxy resin content

PET / epoxy blends

Morphology

The SEM micrographs of the PET / DGEBA / M-CDEA blends cured at 260 °C and at 180 °C are presented in Figure 2. In all the cured blends a phase separated and phase inverted morphology of dispersed epoxy particles in a continuous PET matrix is observed. With

increasing PET content the dispersed epoxy-phase diameter is decreased. This decrease is a combined effect of decreasing the epoxy volume fraction and increasing the viscosity of the solutions upon decreasing the epoxy content. A high viscosity reduces the coarsening of growing epoxy droplets by coalescence effects, resulting in a smaller epoxy particle size as has been shown for other thermoplast / epoxy systems [1,7]. However, the effect of viscosity on the particle size is probably not large because of the relatively low initial viscosities of the PET / epoxy blends, see Figure 1. Next to this, a decrease in the dispersed epoxy particle size is observed with increasing initial cure temperature. Obviously, the increased rate of polymerization of epoxy decreases the time to gelation of the epoxy, at which point the morphology is set and extensive coalescence is prevented.

Figure 2: SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces of PET / epoxy blends cured at 260 °C containing respectively a) 50 wt.%, b) 75 wt.% PET and cured at 180 °C containing respectively c) 50 wt.%, d) 75 wt.% wt.% PET.

Mechanical behaviour

Table 2 shows the flexural properties of the PET / epoxy blends cured at 260 °C and 180 °C versus the blend composition. For the blends cured at 260 °C and for the blends cured at 180 °C the modulus, strength and strain to failure show an increase upon increasing the epoxy content. Next to this it is observed that blends cured at 260 °C overall exhibit a lower flexural strength and strain to failure. Curing at this temperature will cause more chemical degradation of PET to occur by e.g. hydrolysis or aminolysis reaction, resulting in a lower PET molecular

weight. This increase in molecular weight will decrease the mechanical properties such as strength and strain to failure.

Table 2: Flexural mechanical properties of the PET / epoxy blends cured according to cure schedule A (260 °C) and schedule B (180 °C)

PET content [wt.%]	cure schedule A (260 °C)			cure schedule B (180 °C)		
	E [GPa]	σ [MPa]	ϵ [%]	E [GPa]	σ [MPa]	ϵ [%]
50	3.7	103.9	2.8	3.6	127.4	3.6
75	3.9	91.9	2.3	4.1	118.3	2.9
100	4.2	71.0	1.7	4.2	53.9	1.3

Composites based on PET / epoxy blends

Flexural mechanical properties

In Table 3 the flexural mechanical properties of the glass fabric laminates are presented. Since the flexural properties are mainly dominated by the fibre properties, the flexural performance of the PET / epoxy based laminates does not vary much with blend composition. The level of flexural performance confirms that the reactive processing route yields good quality composites with a good impregnation, without any compromise in comparison with unmodified PET based laminates.

Table 3: Flexural mechanical properties of the glass fabric laminates based on PET / epoxy blends cured according to cure schedule A (260 °C) and cure schedule B (180 °C).

PET content [wt.%]	cure schedule A (260 °C)			cure schedule B (180 °C)		
	E [GPa]	σ [MPa]	ϵ [%]	E [GPa]	σ [MPa]	ϵ [%]
50	11.1	320	2.9	11.2	330	3.0
75	11.0	333	3.0	11.7	372	3.2
100	10.1	291	2.9	11.1	321	2.9

In-plane shear properties

In Figure 3 the in-plane shear strength of the glass fabric laminates is shown. Upon increasing the epoxy content in the PET / epoxy matrix a substantial increase in in-plane shear strength can be observed. Next to this, an overall higher shear strength is observed for laminates cured at 180 °C. Since shear properties of composites are mainly determined by the properties of the matrix and the interphase, this increase in shear strength is fully in agreement with the results obtained for the blends as has been shown in Table 2. The fibre - matrix adhesion is also improved significantly by the presence of epoxy resin, which was confirmed by SEM

observations. Next to this, the shear modulus of the laminates is about 2.2 GPa and is hardly dependent on the epoxy content in the matrix.

Figure 3: *In-plane shear strength of glass fabric laminates based on PET / epoxy blends cured according to schedule A: □ 260 °C and schedule B: ■ 180 °C versus the epoxy content. ♦ taken from [8].*

CONCLUSIONS

The application of PET as a matrix material for glass fabric reinforced composites has been studied using epoxy resin as a reactive solvent. Solutions of PET in epoxy resin show low viscosities, from 300 Pa•s for pure PET to approximately 0.1 Pa•s at 60 wt.% epoxy resin. This low melt-viscosity is in the same range as for resins used in SRIM and RTM techniques. In this way, an increase in the rate and level of impregnation of continuous-fibre reinforcements could certainly be achieved by using epoxy resin as a reactive solvent. Upon curing of the PET / epoxy blends phase separation and phase inversion is initiated, resulting in a morphology of dispersed epoxy particles in a continuous PET matrix. The flexural strength and strain to failure of the cured blends increase with increasing epoxy content. Blends cured in the melt at 260 °C show overall lower mechanical properties than blends which are allowed to crystallize at a lower temperature prior to complete curing, because of degradation of PET at this high temperature. The flexural performance of glass fabric laminates based on these blends confirm that the reactive processing route yields good quality composites. The in-plane shear strength of the laminates is increased significantly with increasing epoxy content in the matrix. Moreover, the fibre - matrix adhesion is improved with increasing epoxy content.

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REFERENCES

1. Venderbosch, R.W., Meijer, H.E.H. and Lemstra, P.J., "Processing of intractable polymers using reactive solvents: 1. Poly(2,6-dimethyl-1,4-phenylene ether) / epoxy resin", *Polymer*, Vol.35, No. 20, 1994, pp.4349-4357
2. Venderbosch, R.W., Meijer, H.E.H. and Lemstra, P.J., "Processing of intractable polymers using reactive solvents: 2. Poly(2,6-dimethyl-1,4-phenylene ether) as a matrix material for high performance composites", *Polymer*, Vol. 36, No. 6, 1995, 1167-1178
3. Venderbosch, R.W., Meijer, H.E.H. and Lemstra, P.J., "Processing of intractable polymers using reactive solvents: 3. Mechanical properties of Poly(2,6-dimethyl-1,4-phenylene ether) processed by using various epoxy resin systems", *Polymer*, Vol.36, No. 15, 1995, pp.2903-2913
4. Venderbosch, R.W., Peijs, T., Meijer, H.E.H., and Lemstra, P.J., "Fibre-reinforced composites with tailored interphases using PPE/epoxy blends as a matrix system", *Composites - Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, Vol. 27, No. 9, 1996, pp. 895-905
5. Meijer, H.E.H., Venderbosch, R.W., Goossens, J.G.P. and Lemstra, P.J., "Processing of thermoplastic polymers using reactive solvents", *High Performance Polymers*, Vol. 8, 1996, pp. 133-167
6. Palys, L.H. and Phillips, P.J., "Microkinetics of crystallization in poly(ethylene terephthalate)", *Journal of Polymer Science, Part B: Polymer Physics*, Vol. 18, No. 4, 1980, pp. 829-852
7. Yamanaka, K. and Inoue, T., " Structure development in epoxy resin modified with poly(ether sulphone)", *Polymer*, Vol. 30, No. 4, 1989, pp 662
8. Information Sheet No. FTA 46f, "Fibredux 913", Ciba Geigy, 1991